

MULTISENSORY INTERACTIONS AND SONIFICATION OF IMMUNOLOGY DATA FOR BLIND AND LOW VISION AUDIENCES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents interdisciplinary research exploring multisensory interactions and sonification of immunology data for blind and low vision (BLV) audiences. The authors assert a role for interactive sonification in multisensory display and interactions through exploratory practice-based studio art and music methods. A range of creative works are presented and discussed including tactile and light emitting diode (LED) technology displays, protein sonifications and the development of novel multisensory science books. The paper also reports on a novel interactive sonification technique combining real-time signal processing via a mixture of video and audio domain processing. The authors argue that multisensory interactions offer great potential in explaining immunology data, enabling a wider sphere of access to this knowledge for blind, low vision and diverse needs audiences.

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper reports on interdisciplinary research exploring the potential for interactive sonification in multisensory data representations of immunology for science and inclusion.

The research has been undertaken as part of an ongoing artist residency program exploring immunology at the Rossjohn Infection and Immunity lab, Biomedicine Discovery Institute, Monash University, Australia. The artist in residence program has been running since 2018 by Dr Erica Tandori, a legally blind artist and Professor Jamie Rosjohn. Since 2020, the program has been joined by Dr Stu Favilla, a computer musician/computer interaction designer from Swinburne University of Technology.

The aim of the *Sensory Science Program*, has been to bring the world of immunology through the light microscope to blind, low vision (BLV) and diverse needs audiences. Practice based exploratory research in the form of tactile art making, data visualisations and sonifications has produced a range of data outputs including tactile artworks, protein inspired music, interactive sonifications, multisensory interactions and exhibitions for people with low vision, blindness and diverse needs. The program has staged a number of exhibitions at national and international level.

1.1 Biomolecular Visualization and Multisensory Display

The demand for accessible biomolecular visualization in both science and communication of research, remains evidenced in the work of David Goodsell (at the Center for Computational Structural Biology, CCSB) and the work of Drew Berry (at the

Walter and Eliza Hall Institute, WEHI TV). Both these scientists have strived to create artistic renderings of proteins, immune cells, receptors and their interactions through drawings, watercolours, computer-generated images and animations. They have utilised data from structural biology to create stunning visual works of high scientific accuracy and artistic calibre with global impact in the field of Science.

Goodsell argues a context for *SciArt* or science-based Art; “The idea of borrowing the techniques of fine art for scientific communication has proven useful throughout the history of science and is currently undergoing a renaissance with the SciArt movement. The power of SciArt has perhaps its strongest manifestation in structural biology” (Goodsell 2021, pp. 403). Goodsell’s contribution across two decades has developed software that not only serves to illustrate and describe cells and proteins for publication, but can also be used to test protein interactions, establish new hypotheses and even design new drugs at the molecular level.

A plethora of indispensable computer-generated molecular imaging software are used today, including *PyMol*, *Jmol*, *Chimera*, *Bioblender*, *Proteopedia*, *Protein Data Bank* (RCSB PDB) and *CellPAINT*. However, there is also opportunity for both interactive sonification and new types of data display including multisensory forms. Multisensory display, also defined as *data sensification* (Tak & Toet, 2013; Hogan, 2018; Hogan & Hornecker, 2016), can be defined as the incorporation of at least two modalities and sensory channels employed simultaneously to convey the same piece of information.

Screen-based data visualisation alone has long been known to be limited by the spatiotemporal bandwidth of visual perception, itself affected by occlusion, crowding, clutter, inattention blindness and change blindness (Tak & Toet, 2013). This is also true for virtual reality (VR) and computer assisted virtual environments (CAVEs). There are also a limited number of visual parameters that data can be mapped to, for example colour and saturation, intensity, density and animation frequency. Multisensory display may provide additional tactile and auditory cues (sonification) boosting the saliency of visual features (Tak & Toet, 2013).

1.2 Sonification and Multisensory Interactions for BLV

Sonification has a long tradition of sounding biological data (Munakata, 1995; Dunn, 1992). Sonification has emerged as a useful tool harnessing the pattern recognition power of the brain’s cognitive and perceptual auditory system. Dubus (2013) reviewed over 170 peer reviewed scientific publications of sonification projects and there have been many examples of

protein sonifications where single amino acids, chunks and sequences are mapped to sound melodic phrases. This mapping technique has been applied in recent work including discrimination of protein fold classifications (Bywater & Middleton, 2016) sequence and multiple sequence alignment identification (Martin et al, 2021) and as a preparation of data for machine learning and *de novo* protein design using artificial intelligence for molecular modelling (Yu & Buehler, 2020). Spatial audio sonifications of protein surfaces have recently been achieved (Bouchara & Montes, 2020) for the purposes of protein communication, exhibition and display, including for people with low vision and blindness. These were presented as immersive, binaural spatial audio renderings over headphones utilising head-tracking.

While multisensory display may have the potential to improve the understanding of data pertaining to biomolecular science, there is also the potential for interactive sonification and tactile Art to communicate Science for those with blindness and low vision. Recognising the need for greater inclusion in Astronomy, a number of innovative projects have been developed for people with blindness and or low vision (BLV). For example, *The Wonder Dome* education program in the UK has presented a range of tactile exhibitions for BLV people including *Accessible Astronomy* (Perez-Montero) 3D renderings of NASA's Hubble Telescope Images (Arcand et.al 2019) (see figure 1) Braille maps of star constellations and tactile 3D prints of the Whirlpool Galaxy (Messier catalogue M51). Although sonifications of Astronomy data have also been exhibited by Wonder Dome, none of the tactile exhibitions incorporated interactive sonification as a multisensory display channel.

Figure 1. *Hubble Telescope Images rendered as 3D Objects*

As there is currently little understanding as to whether multisensory representation of immunology data is effective in conveying information to people with diverse needs, low vision or blindness the authors developed two exigent questions. The first research question was framed to explore the creation of exhibitions for people with BLV: (RQ1) How can multisensory approaches to explaining immunology data, enable a wider sphere of access to this knowledge for BLV audiences? Also, as the project was taking place in a biomolecular research laboratory exploring infection and immunity with access to scientists, a second research question was formed to explore potential solutions and novelty in the scientific domain: (RQ2) How can multisensory data representations boost the saliency of immunology data for scientific research, investigation and dissemination?

2. METHODOLOGY

To answer the research questions an interdisciplinary approach was adopted utilising practice-based art and computer music studio methods for exploration, experimentation and inductive theory building. To review and evaluate the studio explorations, a range of design methods were also adopted from interaction design, inclusive and participatory design, user centred design and iterative software design. The methodology was inspired by the eight-step multisensory-design approach developed by Schifferstein (2011) at Delft University of Technology and also drew on Multisensory Design approaches including Pagliano (2012) Hogan and Hornecker (2016). As the artist in residence (and coauthor of this paper) is a legally blind visual artist, the research also aimed to directly harness the lived experience of vision loss.

A range of research objectives were defined for a number of chronologically staged overlapping research phases:

1. Explore multisensory forms through Art-based Practice,
2. Investigate the potential for interactive sonification in multisensory representations of immunology data,
3. Develop multisensory data interactions utilising a) tactile and visual, b) audio and visual, c) tactile, visual and audio forms,
4. Undertake qualitative and quantitative analyses of multisensory works evaluating data sensitification for scientific communication and data saliency,
5. Utilise inclusive and participatory design methods with low vision participants exploring multisensory modalities including tactile, sonification, auditory, olfactory, visual, haptic and computer interactions, and
6. Stage exhibitions of creative works evaluating feedback from participant groups including Scientists and low vision, blind and diverse needs communities.

This paper reports on research exploring the first three objectives. As the research has been undertaken in Melbourne Australia, the COVID lockdowns and restrictions have precluded exhibitions and design workshops with BLV participants. As these research stages are completed, it is anticipated the findings will be reported in future publications.

3. MULTISENSORY ART, MUSIC AND INTERACTIONS

3.1 Tactile and Visual

Many BLV people have partial vision, only a tiny amount of central vision or see through their peripheral field. Many can see colour and many have a limited knowledge of the retina, its cellular anatomy and function. This is particularly true for children, elderly people who have lost their vision much later in life and importantly the carers, family members and friends that may also be attending exhibitions with a BLV person. The Tactile Retina map is a three-foot wide multisensory representation of the human retina and macula (see fig. 2) which sits at the central part of the retina. The map was created so that people with vision impairment could identify tactually how the eye is structured, and where diseases of the eye that cause blindness can often be located.

The Tactile Retina map contains all the layers of the retina represented as separate and distinctive tactile layers, including a Retinal Pigment Epithelial (RPE) layer made of red dyed couscous grains to represent the granular lining of rich blood cells, a Brush's membrane made up of tiny plastic eyes and distinctive ganglion and other cells found in the interior chambers of the vitreous chamber.

Circuitry of red, green and blue fluorescent electric wire (*elwire*) loops flashing on and off represent the photoreceptor cells of the retina, an absence of which occurs in the map to denote the area of the macula where photoreceptors fall away. The *elwire* loops were controlled by an embedded Arduino and ran along the length of the tactile retina map coursing into a single point which describes, both visually and tactually, where the optic nerve travels into the brain. Timing periods for green, blue, red and white loops were set to 300-500 millisecond to simulate the firing of rods and cones whereas a cycle of flashing of 20 millisecond for braided white and blue *elwire* simulated the synaptic flow throughout the ganglion cell network into the optic nerve.

Figure 2. Tactile and visual map of the retina with embedded *elwire* loops

A range of other tactile works with light emitting diode (LED) displays were created exploring immunology data themes. Addressable colour (RGB) LED strips were utilised to display RNA data as sequenced chains. Arduino microcontrollers were utilised first and then Raspberry Pi's were utilised where the graphical programming Pure Data could be put to use to parse protein data into integer streams and then remapped to RGB colour tables. These colour data streams were then output to addressable LED strips.

A strip of 60 addressable RGB LEDs was utilised to cycle through the entire RNA sequence of COVID2-SARs where each of the four bases adenine, thymine, guanine and cytosine (ATGC) could be assigned its own distinct colour. The strip of 60 LEDs displayed the 30,000 base sequence in 498 sets of 60 LEDs with an adjustable cycle rate. A smaller strip of 10 LEDs utilised a sequence of 3,000 separate light patterns (see figure 4). This way HIV and COVID2-SARS RNA data streams were both explored through tactile light displays incorporated into virus capsid models. The models explored a range of structural hexagonal forms to simulate capsid hexamer protein surfaces and included chicken-wire forms dipped with glue and couscous, glass beads hot glued to chicken wire and small LED strips wrapped in beeswax.

3.2 Audio and Visual Explorations

The RNA data sets explored were also parsed into corresponding data streams for sonification. Firstly, the RNA data was parsed into a four pitch MIDI stream which was then brought into a modular synthesiser for explorative mapping and music making. A wide range of mappings was explored through the modular system which was built around a Strega monophonic synthesiser made by the modular company Make Noise (see figure 3).

In the modular synthesiser environment, pitch, control and even audio signals can be mixed and mapped directly to parameter patch points via physical cables. Via the connection of a number of cables throughout the system a range of complex patches utilising multi mappings of the pitch stream afforded the creation of both sonification and electronic music. A range of digital signal processing patches were also developed in Max GEN for the Befaco *Lich* programmable module including Karplus Strong and comb filter delays, where the stream of RNA MIDI pitches was mapped to delay time, comb-filter delay time, low-pass filter cutoff, granular and time points for looping effects.

Figure 3. Modular System featuring Make Noise Strega and Befaco Lich used for RNA Sonification and music creation

This phase of the research also saw the construction of a five-foot tall HIV capsid model utilising both hexamer and pentamer shapes with papier-mâché. The giant capsid (see figure 4) was intended to be a 3D screen for a data projection mapping scheduled to be presented as part of the National Science Week exhibitions. To simulate the protein surface the model was glue down and covered with foam bean bag filling and spray painted in a bright white pigment spray paint. Protein coloured light sequences and synchronised streams of audio were displayed in the laboratory only, as unfortunately the exhibitions were cancelled due to COVID lockdowns.

Figure 4. 10 LED strip in capsid model and Giant HIV Capsid projection project

3.3 Multisensory Interactive Science Books

The advent of COVID quickly forced an adaptation of delivery since lockdowns and restrictions (in a city which endured the longest periods of lockdown in the world) no longer allowed for public gatherings and exhibitions at university or other venues. In response the program created a set of multisensory interactive science books, which could be distributed to individuals, small groups or online via a website.

A government grant was awarded in 2021 to produce the books titled *My Goodness*, which celebrated the 2021 United Nations International Year of Fruits and Vegetables. Given the theme, the books content covered a range of topics related to the health of the human digestive system and related issues of infection, immunity and gut related diseases. Content was produced in collaboration with scientists specialising in this field from Monash University Biomedicine Discovery Institute.

The books were created in A3 size format with laminated pages, (for easy wipe down as a COVID measure) on a foam core base, tactile artworks, large print, braille supplements and interactive software generated by optical fiducials scanned by the ReactiVision software from the ReactTable project (Jordà et al, 2007). Fiducials were utilized for page numbers and as buttons for navigational scrolling through audio elements including narration, music and sonifications (see figure 6).

Tactile artworks throughout the books include ‘braille’ inspired molecular structures such as vitamin A and vitamin B metabolites, tactile structures of immune cells, viruses, bacteria, and the digestive system. A combination of 3D printing and handmade cell sculptures appear throughout the book’s pages with audio text to accompany each topic and associated artwork. A range of textures and materials was used to create the multisensory artefacts, conveying complexity and interest for blind and low vision readers. The artworks were designed to be slightly raised in order to enable textural features, while also being flat enough for the pages to close properly.

Figure 5. Example multisensory book with tactile protein and fiducial marker in top righthand corner of left facing page

A major component of the books was the use of interactive sonification of tactile artworks throughout the book, which could be activated by touching (covering) the open page’s fiducial. The books were designed to sit on individual inclined (30 degree) stands. The book stands also included headphone jacks and Mac mini computers driving software interactions. The books provided an opportunity to explore the combination of tactile, visual, audio (music and narration) and sonifications. The close intimate exhibition setting also afforded the opportunity to

further explore the role of sonification in tactile and visual sensory artworks. Could the artworks also be sonified? Would the sonification support the understanding of the visual and tactile forms?

The Mac mini (M1 processor) computers were highly capable and a large step up from the embedded computing methods the project had so far explored e.g. Arduinos and Raspberry Pis. The increase in computational processing also afforded the opportunity to sonify data in real-time and because the books were utilizing an optical scanning system via a webcam there was also the opportunity to sonify the tactile images themselves. Although there are a number of studio software tools that can resynthesize an image e.g. Metasynth by U&I Software there are few examples of commercial software capable of this task.

Therefore, the authors developed a dedicated software tool specifically for his task in the Max MSP Jitter data flow graphical programming language. After some investigation and searching, an FFT resynthesis software algorithm developed by composer Zack Settel was adapted to resynthesize a live video camera feed. The patch featured an “ioscbank~” or *interpolated oscillator bank* object which was configured to provide a separate audio waveform oscillator for each vertical pixel in the video image. The image stream was then read into a sample buffer created using the “peak~” object and making use of Zack Settel’s implementation of a Hanning filter example developed by Ben Jacobs.

A windowing function was created using a half sine waveform located in an audio buffer to scroll across a processing window. This was done to provide a flexible audio grain size to match each horizontal pixel of the video stream and to also blur each audio grain and eliminate digital audio artefacts from the sonification. Lastly the video data, window functions and interpolated oscillator banks were processed using a stereo fast Fourier transform (FFT) and *inverse* FFT pair function.

Figure 6. Video image sonification software GUI showing processed image of a tactile protein artwork (pictured in figure 5). Note the 253 band multislider spectral filter interface, resynthesis waveform editor and video image scaling parameters

Initial tests of the audio engine were successful, and the engine would scroll play through vertical bands of video pixels in real time. The brightness of each pixel corresponded to the gain of the corresponding resynthesis grain and horizontal span of 1920 pixels could be scroll played over an adjustable range of 2 to 20 seconds. However, the audio was often extremely rich and inharmonic, resulting in harsh and displeasing sonifications.

Therefore, the FFT and inverse FFT processing chain was modified to include a spectral filter including 253 bands of 24 dB attenuation. This was coupled to a multislider GUI to facilitate mouse drawing of spectral filters. Control variables were then developed to adjust the horizontal grain time scale and additionally scale the output range of the FFT bands. Volume control and a third-party reverb abstraction were added to the sonification engine and a set of variables were created for real-time control screen-based GUIs (see figure 6).

Figure 7 *Phidget888 microcontroller physical console interfacing a mixture of dials, joysticks, mode switches and pressure sensor controllers for interactive sonification control.*

As the Max language also included a comprehensive range of video objects the image stream was also processed in real-time. Luminance keying was utilized to remove the background page of the multisensory books and brightness, contrast and luminance processing functions were used to invert tactile images, lifting and accentuating surface details for sonification. To further facilitate experimentation a combination of sonification parameters together with video processing parameters were mapped to a physical controller built around a Phidget888 microcontroller. This allowed for tweaking and multiparameter adjustment to be made in real-time and greatly sped up the process of discovery and learning of what the image based sonification software could achieve.

4. DISCUSSION

The project is in early stages and is limited by a lack of input from BLV participants and design studies, however a number of challenges and findings came to light throughout the practice based research. Firstly, the inclusion of linear LED lightstrip displays can not only brighten and make tactile artworks much more appealing, they can also provide time-based data to tactile models. These displays can also be synchronous with MIDI data for music and sonifications. Although protein data such as RNA strands are huge and their structure remains incomprehensible, the LED lightstrips can be located inside tactile models and provide some small measure of scientific data and authenticity to the multisensory experience. However, LED displays can very effectively communicate time based cellular functions such as the firing of retinal rods and cones and the synaptic flow of ganglion fibres into the optic nerve. They can be adapted to tactile artworks large and small and create beautiful and compelling works.

Secondly, real-time video image sonification can be utilized to sonify artworks and images for multisensory display and interactions. This work is only in its preliminary stage and as it

sonify's luminance data from an image frame, colour information is as yet redundant. Nonetheless the technique created appealing and interesting sonifications of images and tactile artworks. The way images and tactile images are read requires study and it was clear to the researchers that there was a perceptual multisensory mismatch between the linear sonification read from left to right and the intuitive exploration of the works through touch. It also took time to learn how to hear the image over the visual or tactile perceptual experience. Multisensory interactions may require a level of familiarity or literacy to be used effectively. However, it was also noted that two very similar appearing tactile protein models of Vitamin A and Vitamin B metabolites each sounded very distinct once sonified. Therefore sonification can play an important role in differentiation and comprehension of ambiguous tactile and visual images in multisensory interactions.

Although sonifying images using FFT resynthesis methods is nothing new the addition of image processing parameters alongside traditional resynthesis parameters created an effective method to find appealing and comprehensible sonifications. Luminance keying and brightness, contrast and luminance preprocessing prior to analysis and audio resynthesis afforded fast and efficient explorations of trial and error. The inclusion of a hardware controller for multiparameter control further increase the rate of explorations.

The use of modular synthesis for sonification exploration poses challenges for scientific research and discourse. The construction of a modular synthesizer and its patching are extremely difficult to reproduce. Time spent with the modular system was considered nonetheless inspiring and extremely rewarding and the process generated many ideas including the development of a hardware controller to interact with the image sonification software. The work generated around seven hours of music excerpts of which form a general soundtrack for the interactive multisensory science books. The use of the dedicated hardware control was found to speed up the process of improving sonifications, making them clearer to comprehend and more appealing to listen to. The ability to modulate video and audio parameters together from a single device is novel.

5. CONCLUSION

This research explored a range of multisensory forms and interaction with sonification through practice-based studio methods and investigated the potential for interactive sonification in multisensory representations of immunology data. A range of multisensory data interactions were developed exploring a) tactile and visual, b) audio and visual, c) tactile, visual and audio forms of multisensory display of immunology data.

In response to COVID lockdowns and restrictions, the project has developed a novel interaction format in the form of a multisensory book for BLV audiences.

The project has much more work to do and the sonification method has yet to be controllable via fiducial interactions in the books themselves. Plans for the next stages of software development include mappings of tangible fiducials for jog wheel sample playback control and sonification strategies for colour information in images. The use of conductive paint and embedded computing to create touch interactive artworks also needs to be explored. This may be an effective way to address the multisensory perceptual mismatches between sonifications and tactile proteins (see figure 8).

There is also opportunity to bring other forms of protein and interactive sonification into the books. This will involve systematically reviewing the research literature of protein sonification (and musification) to create a range of protein sonification techniques. Co-creation and interaction workshops with BLV participants are also planned as too are exhibitions of the multisensory books throughout schools, community centres and organisations catering for BLV people.

In conclusion, multisensory display and interactions offer great potential explaining immunology data, enabling a wider sphere of access to this knowledge for BLV and sighted audiences alike.

Figure 8. Tactile proteins

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